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Art in Denim Fashion: Impacts on Youth in Bangladesh

Juhan Md Shabbir Hussain^{1*}, Lui Fang², Mostakim Md Masrur Ammar³

¹³ School of Fine Art, Masters of Art, Huzhou University, China

² Professor, School of Fine Art, Huzhou University, China.

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ABSTRACT

Denim fashion and art collaborations have been increasing popular in recent years. While these collaborations have strategic importance and are unique from previous collaborations, recent literature implies that there is a gap, in the context of such collaborations, this hunt for target to figure out what's causing the problem is ongoing. From the point of view of a modern partnership between denim fashion and artwork, the customer, the retailer, brand and the youth. The goal of today's research is to establish a new norm of limitless reuse by reducing denim fabric at all levels of art and education. This research for dreams to discover the intent of the contemporary collaboration of denim fashion and artwork from the perspective of business and have an impact on the youth in Bangladesh. Discover more about examples of denim trend structure and art collaborations from the past and present, investigate the contemporary and business company magnitude of the denim trend and collaborative artwork work. Consider the numerous denim vogue and art collaborative products available. From the designers, customers and the youth perspective, managerial insights are generated. On the implementation of fashion and the promotion of appropriate trend-setting techniques designers/brands who want to be a part of such collaborative arrangement, special guidelines for Bangladesh marketers, have an impact on the youth of Bangladesh. We begin to realize that labeling a style of art as inferior and frivolous is far too glib, let alone inaccurate and unfair. Since the beginning of the twentieth century, style has played a central role in popularizing art. In many instances, "Denim fashion" is to grant structure or shape to; alter, transform; make, or collect in many instances with the use creativity and ingenuity; the dominant fashion trend (as in clothing) for a specific period of time; a garment in such a style. The definitions of "art" and "denim fashion" are similar. Yet, in present day years, the denim style is no longer regarded as a work of art, but rather as a regular and beneficial quality of clothing. Apparel or as a style and youth of Bangladesh accepting and carry out art in Denim fashion.

Keywords

Art, Denim, Jeans, clothing, youth fashion, impact of fashion.

Introduction

Art in Denim; the latest technique developed in Denim

Classical denim is a sturdy, long-lasting heavy cloth made from cotton, developed in a twill weave and woven from coarse indigo dyed or sulphur dyed warp and gray un-dyed weft yarn. Conventional woven denim is now not as gentle in texture as different knit fabrics, and so applications of art in denim in trend plans that need elasticity are limited. Since denim takes up a giant share of the market in the current world, and knitted material has various properties that permit it to suit physique shapes and be comfortable, a new way of combining the two methods of material development to create a "Denim effect using knit structures" has been developed. A recent survey on children's denim merchandise confirmed that comfort, softness, convenience, care, light weight, and material excellence are among the attributes regarded to be essential with the aid of each mother, father, and child. Knitted denim material, with its refined structure, clear lines, soft, breathable comfort, and quality skinny points, is the final answer, inserting style and relief into balance. Shine with this new trend. Knitted denim is now not solely an elegant cowboy's difficult exterior, but is becoming popular in an increasing number of crowded denim markets, anxious to seize new commercial enterprise opportunities. As the varieties of art in knitted denim continue to expand, art in knitted denim can be used for absorbent, antibacterial, and fitness care purposes, as well as in T-shirts, kid's clothing, sleepwear, underwear, sportswear, informal wear, fashion, etc.

Literature Review

Collaborations between denim fashion and artwork in contemporary advertising include elements of fashion, design, art, customer behavior, manufacturers, and Bangladeshi adolescence. Accordingly, all these fields are investigated in this literature review. This helps to appreciate the difficulty of trend graphs and artwork collaborations and obtain the quintessential heritage information associated with this issue. More importantly, this assessment can grant a speculation of shaping contemporary inventive collaboration in trend advertising, which is examined in subsequent look ups and acts as the basis of creating a precise idea about the collaboration between the denim trend and art. In this study, the opinions are grouped into seven parts:

- I. Perception of denim fashion. This section contains opinions on the meaning of trend as an abstract concept and the evolution of trend as apparel fashion throughout trend history.
- II. The ancient inter-fusion of denim fashion and art. This illustrates the mutual affinity of artists and trend designers for each other's fields;
- III. Theoretical appreciation of the fashion-art relationship. This section displays the results of the most recent search on this topic;
- IV. Impact of counterculture motion on artwork and the purchaser's way of life in postmodern society. This section discusses specific aspects of art and customer culture in the context of postmodern society.
- V. Characteristics of modern trends and design. This section presents industrial background in order to identify cutting-edge creative collaborative trends;

- VI. Features of modern brands. This phase offers insights into the collaboration of trend format and artwork from the brand's perspective;
- VII. Specific issues concerning artist identity this phase examines the standards connected with the lookup from the artist's perspective.

Framework

Research follows the descriptive analytical approach and utility study. There are a number of lookup processes adopted for this study. They encompass a historic paradigm and a modern-day standpoint that offers an evaluation of writings on the topics of fashion, art, and denim trend art. Furthermore, I carried out an Internet survey of Art and Fashion university students where I gathered their opinions about trends as art. I also, performed what I called an experiment in which the true development of a garment was primarily based on the designs and methods used with the aid of Issey Miyake. When learning statistics for my historic paradigm, these sources included a number of authors, designers, and even costume reformers who share my faith in the denim trend as art. We used it in jeans' ornament designs and defined how it can be employed. Most of our tapestry plan thoughts are utilized for women's and men's jackets and dresses, due to the fact that they have extensive areas and are more noticeable than ordinary denim pants. Thus, the scale of ornament on jackets and clothes would be large and more influential. The interaction of plan factors and principles, fabric properties, adaptation and modification of format ideas are all critical. Stone (2001) emphasizes that historical fashions are rich sources of graphic inspiration, with designers reinterpreting historical themes in novel ways and the youth of Bangladesh as well. A few of the questions are as follows: "In your very own words, what is fashion? What can be fashion? ", "In your personal words, what is art? What kinds of things can qualify as art?" "Do you think a denim garment is artwork if it's displayed in a museum or gallery?" and "Do you think something is artwork just because it's called art?" The lookup based "experiment" that I performed indicates the transition to when and how the denim trend can end up art.

I do this by first developing a trend diagram or drawing (in artwork terms) of the garment I am designing. Next, from the sketch, I created the garment in a three-dimensional structure (sculpture) out of wire. Then, I made a 2D x 3D structure (sculpture) out of wire, but I included positive areas of the structure with paper to fill in some of the poor spaces. Finally, I made the originally designed garment out of fabric by searching for previously made portions. I based the foundations of my scan totally on the trend designer, Issey Miyake. I selected Issey Miyake due to the fact that he makes use of a lot of creative factors in his portions and he believes trends to be art. He states, "Always human beings say that is artwork or that is design...But to exhibit it is the same. It's a top notch pleasure.

Experimental Results

Women, who choose woman's denim colorings due to their worn look, pick out the fashions of light blue jeans, which provide a sturdy feeling, and are fashionable. The jeans were geared up with three front and two rear pockets, referred to as a 5-pocket style. Besides, the model has a small piped pocket in every rear pocket.

However, the Slim and Super Stretch models fashionably match towards the body. The cool button-front mini skirt Made from the famed denim trouser, it offers a nod to homemade-in-as the DIY structure is reconstructed from men's jeans. The patterns demonstrate a women's blue denim skirt high with waist ripped, holes, pockets and body-con as a mini-jeans skirt. The skirts are also made of distressed denim with a chewed hem, which gives them a just-right excessive waistline and flattering silhouette. The A-line structure makes it a dependent style. Many stores make full-scale efforts to reveal their involvement in closed-loop recycling as self-motivation through supportive customers to retrieve old used denim for new ones and drastically change these garments as raw materials. It can be combined with both fashionable and everyday denim to create comfortable and fantastic looks. Trendy attire appears stunning at any second. It's all straight ahead to make use of and mix. With sneakers and equipment, it would possibly get elegant pictures. Denim apparel is very stylish. In any case, [Egyetem \(2015\)](#) defined that due to the fact of the application of the special craft technique, jeans today are genuine. The majority of denim materials are artificially dwindled and sorrowful in order to achieve a fashionable, worn-in look. This method can create honeycombs such as dwindled traces at the back of the knees, faded streaks around the crotch area, diminished traces at the thigh, knees tearing, abrasions, as an example. Those fading patterns and catastrophic patterns on jeans is a fashion of "personalizing". All the time standards that will be very comfortable and simple, but also stunning, as demonstrated by fashionable jeans Stylish and Casual Dresses for Women confirmed in Couture Fall 2016-Viktor & Rolf. Made entirely of restyled denim. Inspired with the aid of a Turkish people's wear coat with a true shape. From a random pocket to a challenging waistband. Jeans costumes stimulated on workers' clothing, made of remodeled denim and perfectly completed with antique linen. Jeans costumes stimulated the reform of blues and skirts from two trousers. The trend of distinctive jeans took place in 2018 when the American company CIE Denim had a curious thought when it came to the use of the primary piece of all wardrobes, developing a kind of "inverted jeans", inspired by the success of the "Stranger Things" series on Netflix. According to the brand, the thinking behind the idea was to characterize the inverted world and the Nineteen Eighties that are portrayed in the sequence and pay homage to some characters. Made the use of approximately eight pairs of re-purposed second-hand jeans a landfill diversion. In the Milan trend exhibit fall 2018 by trend fashion designer Angel Chen, each pair of jeans is undoubtedly unpicked by hand. Character sample pieces, which are then reconfigured into couture fashion design. Enterprise in general, and particularly to improve working conditions in international manufacturing. The precaution for denim redesigning is primarily based on four factors: cloth durability, cloth health, fabric re- cyclability, and material traceability. Durability increasing the common worn variety of the use of time-worn garments offers a significant possibility to preserve the price and lay out waste.

Objective

The youth purchaser is a full-size supply of the problem in realizing a sustainable trend in the industry. Fashion clients are ravenous for stylish garments. Consumers want to be free of the blame, guilt, or duty of cleaning

their closets on a regular basis. Actually, it is more of a bodily alternative than a philosophical problem. Low prices, top design, and good-quality trend garments imply larger purchases, which makes it difficult to agree with the notion of the remaining struggle between them and the environment. Achieving predetermined dreams is evolving from merely the grasp of merchandise for manufacture to wider problem-solving, management, and strategic major approaches. Some of these current tactics include redesign, or even provider format and design thinking. With rising new information, these will create thereunder fined user-design experiences. As a result, it is to redecorate denim in general and denims in particular. The existing lookup will provide information to the student about the trend diagram in its unique format and the beginner trend format in general. However, to innovate new denim fashion with well-balanced proportions and pleasing aesthetic appeal, designers may pay close attention to the relationship between the hip, the peak (inseam), and the leg opening areas. It is clear that the proportion between the hips and the leg opening of the flared mannequin played an essential position in the wearer's image. Presently, human beings are content material to be given something greater with ease as "art" if it is in a museum, gallery, or studio. However, as I mentioned above, trend shares many similarities with art in terms of evaluation rather than definition. Another instance would be that one can use many extraordinary mediums to create trend clothes, as in art.

Conclusion

Any style, to name it evergreen, is a fashion that ought to in no way vanish with any season. One should be continuously up to date on what is going out of fashion. Furthermore, it is not uncommon for ancient developments to resurface in a modern context. The bodily look of apparel has been shown to impact consumers' reviews and purchasing decisions. Therefore, the poor impact of the trend enterprise on our planet requests that humans stem from the manufacturing of raw substances to the disposal of a garment after its first use, attempting to decrease these impacts. We can emphasize that the factors of creativity, personality, and cultural heritage are nevertheless taking part in a very vital function in our proposal for designs. As a result, it is expected that this discovery will aid future research into the records of Bangladeshi arts and ornament designs. On the other hand, it is critical to examine various aspects of the social significance of the hand-woven tapestry. However, we strive to open up a new horizon for designers to use the spirit of innovation that is entirely based on records and heritage, in the hope that our strategy will shed some light on a new vogue for denim decorations. If an historic tapestry is no longer maintained or is changed with the aid of something else, such as factory-made re- productions of indigenous fabrics, then not solely does the cloth way of life itself disappear, but additionally, the cultural way of life disappears alongside with it.

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